

Dry Needling as a Therapeutic Approach for Reducing Pain in Musculoskeletal Disorders: a Literature Review

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Abstract

Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) present significant health challenges globally, affecting individuals across various age groups and occupational sectors. Dry needling (DN) has gained popularity as a treatment modality for MSDs, but its effectiveness warrants ongoing assessment. This literature review aims to evaluate the efficacy of DN in managing MSDs by analyzing secondary data from relevant research studies. The review focuses on studies assessing DN's impact on pain reduction in MSD cases, with participants being individuals suffering from these conditions. Results indicate that DN significantly reduces pain associated with MSDs. However, limitations such as the small number of relevant studies and variations in methodologies and populations could influence the findings. The review concludes that DN is effective in alleviating pain in the short term and highlights its potential as a viable treatment option for MSDs. These insights underscore the importance of incorporating DN into treatment plans while considering the need for further research to confirm its benefits.

Keywords: dry needling, musculoskeletal disorders, musculoskeletal pain, physical therapy

INTRODUCTION

Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are a major occupational health issue affecting men and women of all ages globally and across all sectors of activity at similar rates. The World Health Organization (WHO) has reported MSDs as a leading cause of disability and limitations that significantly impact daily life and work performance.^{1,2} Musculoskeletal disorders are a group of conditions affecting bones, joints, muscles, and connective tissues that can cause pain and decreased function. Chronic pain and loss of function are the primary mechanisms leading to disability and unemployment due to musculoskeletal disorders.³

MSDs can arise from the interaction of physical and ergonomic risk factors, such as heavy biomechanical loads, repetitive movements, or static postures. Additionally, individual factors such as gender and being overweight, as well as psychological factors like workplace stress, high work demands, low social support, overall job strain, or job

dissatisfaction, can influence the onset of MSDs. Social and occupational factors, such as workplace design, standing, twisting or straining the body, working posture, repetitive movements, or the forces required to perform job tasks and exposure to vibration, also play a role in the causes of MSDs.⁴

MSDs are classified into two types: specific and non-specific. Specific musculoskeletal disorders have clinically clear symptoms, while non-specific musculoskeletal disorders present with pain without clear evidence of a specific abnormality.²

Workers in various occupations experience health burdens related to severe musculoskeletal pain and work-related injuries, collectively referred to as work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs). These disorders are a group of preventable conditions that affect muscles, tendons, and nerves. The increasing prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among at-risk physicians has been described as "an

impending epidemic" and "the tip of an iceberg."

Many cross-sectional studies report that over 80% of at-risk physicians experience severe pain while performing procedures; the prevalence of tendinitis and carpal tunnel syndrome is also observed to be high, although estimates vary significantly depending on the study.⁵ Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are highly common among healthcare professionals. The prevalence of MSDs has been studied across several health professions, with prevalence rates exceeding 80% reported among physiotherapists, massage therapists, nurses, midwives, dentists, and surgeons. The high prevalence of MSDs is directly related to their practices, which involve varied tasks and high physical demands. Many studies have highlighted the use of awkward and often static postures, especially among surgeons and physiotherapists.⁶

The prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) among physiotherapists is 63.9% (most common locations: lower back, shoulder, neck), while among physiotherapy students, it is 46.5% (most common locations: lower back, neck, upper back).⁷ Other studies have also reported that 58.9% of dentists experience musculoskeletal pain, while the prevalence of physical complaints among laparoscopic surgeons is 74%. However, low response rates and high variability across studies leave uncertainties, suggesting an actual prevalence between 22% and 74%.^{8,9}

Another study has documented a high annual incidence rate of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), ranging from 40% to 95%, in at least one body part or region among Asian nurse populations. In Western populations, the most significantly affected body parts are the lower back, neck, and shoulders, with incidence rates ranging from 29% to 64%

for the lower back, 34% to 63% for the neck, and 17% to 75% for the shoulders. Conversely, a narrative literature review on MSDs among female nurses indicates that the knee and ankle/foot regions are the most frequently affected areas. The prevalence of MSDs in the knee area ranges from 7.5% to 77%, while in the ankle, the prevalence ranges from 3.2% to 100%. The prevalence of MSDs in the lower leg (shin) is lower, with figures between 8.5% and 10.5%, while in the thigh/hip area, the prevalence ranges from 11% to 100%.²

To prevent musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), measures implemented include identifying risk factors reported by workers or observed in the workplace, which are then measured using appropriate instruments. Once risk factors are identified, prevention strategies focus on monitoring the incidence of disorders and exposure to high-risk factors. Some effective approaches in preventing MSDs include improving overall workplace health, as studies show a link between individual risk factors such as smoking, being overweight, and poor physical fitness with MSDs. Additionally, collaboration with experts from various fields such as engineering and psychology is necessary to address MSD-related issues holistically, involving all employees and representatives.

Identifying individual risk factors is also crucial for providing training, administrative controls, and raising awareness of factors such as age, gender, smoking habits, physical activity, and previous history of MSDs. Other risk factors to consider include various non-occupational activities, such as sports and household chores, as well as systemic diseases like rheumatoid arthritis or diabetes. Furthermore, promoting a healthy lifestyle by engaging in regular exercise, maintaining good posture, safe lifting techniques, and reducing repetitive

movements is also essential in preventing MSDs.⁴

Compromised musculoskeletal health can lead to acute and chronic pain, burdens on other health domains, physical limitations involving loss of participation and withdrawal from usual social, community, and work activities, as well as reduced quality of life and well-being, including mental well-being.¹⁰ According to studies, pharmacological options for MSDs have proven ineffective and have side effects that make long-term use difficult, making a multidimensional approach involving patient education, behavioral therapy, exercise, and pain management advisable.¹¹

Dry needling is an additional treatment option in a multidimensional approach that has the potential to be used long-term for reducing pain and disability in this population, which has been extensively researched in several conditions.¹¹ Dry needling (DN) is a common technique used to address musculoskeletal issues. The technique involves inserting a thin needle through the skin, subcutaneous tissue, and muscle. This puncture technique induces a local muscle contraction, helping to relax the treated area. Consequently, DN therapy can reduce local muscle tension and relieve pain in the affected area.¹²

Dry needling can be classified in various ways. Based on the depth of needle insertion, needling can be referred to as superficial and deep, and based on the structure being punctured, it can be classified as trigger point dry needling, fascial needling, and others.¹³

According to several theories, the mechanisms underlying the effects of dry needling can be explained as follows. First, dry needling is believed to increase blood flow to the targeted area, such as the Achilles tendon, which aids tissue healing by providing better blood supply. Additionally, dry needling is also said to reduce the formation of taut bands in the

target tissue, allowing for the recovery of sarcomere and endomysium length. This theory posits that as tension decreases, the tissue becomes more elastic and can recover naturally.¹³ Moreover, dry needling can reduce spontaneous electrical activity in the sensory nerves around the trigger point, which in turn can lead to the restoration of normality at the neuromuscular junction. In addition to mechanical impacts, this therapy can also cause biochemical changes by suppressing high concentrations of H⁺ ions, neurotransmitters, cytokines, and chemokines involved in inflammatory and pain responses. Lastly, there is also a view that the needle puncture action in dry needling can affect the pain gate mechanism, reducing pain perception and enhancing the body's response to painful experiences. Thus, dry needling can work through various interrelated mechanisms to reduce pain and improve healing processes in patients with diverse musculoskeletal conditions.¹³

An increasing number of physiotherapists in the United States and globally are adopting the use of dry needling to treat musculoskeletal pain. As the popularity of dry needling continues to grow among physiotherapists, it is important to continually review existing evidence to support or oppose its effectiveness.¹⁴ Additionally, following the Evidence-Based Medicine approach, the effectiveness of DN in everyday practice seems insufficient and not highly recognized, as indicated by two reliable systematic reviews with meta-analyses.¹⁵

Although dry needling therapy has seen significant developments in pain management, there remains uncertainty regarding its effectiveness. While some studies have demonstrated potential in reducing musculoskeletal pain, more consistent and robust evidence is still needed to support these claims. Moreover, the lack of evidence on the effectiveness

of this technique remains a major concern.^{16,17}

Based on these findings, musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are a significant and widespread health issue globally, affecting workers across various sectors and causing chronic pain and functional loss that impact daily life and work performance. The high prevalence of MSDs among healthcare professionals highlights the urgency of effectively understanding and addressing this condition. The use of dry needling as one approach in managing musculoskeletal pain has increased, but its effectiveness remains debated in the medical literature. Therefore, it is essential to conduct a comprehensive literature review on this topic to clarify existing evidence, evaluate the effectiveness of various interventions, and identify optimal prevention and treatment strategies. This literature review study focuses on assessing the effectiveness of dry needling in MSD cases, particularly its role in pain relief.

METHODS

The research approach used is a literature review, employing secondary

data in the form of analysis of research journals discussing the use of dry needling in patients with musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs). Journal searches were conducted on the PubMed database using the keywords "dry needling," "musculoskeletal disorders," and "musculoskeletal." From 20 journals obtained from the search results, seven journals relevant to the topic of the literature review were selected through category grouping. The grouping categories included study design, research subjects, intervention, outcomes, and year of publication. The criteria for journal selection were randomized control trial designs, subjects with work-related or non-work-related MSDs, dry needling intervention, outcomes with relevant quantitative data, and publications within the last 10 years (January 2014 - July 2024). Abstracts were then analyzed, and irrelevant studies were eliminated. Filtering based on full-text reading and reference scanning was conducted before the literature review analysis was finally carried out. The flowchart of article screening process is showed on figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the Article Screening Process

RESULT

From 20 journals obtained from the search results, seven journals relevant to the topic of the literature review were selected

through category grouping. The review results are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Review results

Title	Sample	Intervention	Measurement	Result
Benefits of dry needling of myofascial trigger points on autonomic function and photoelectric plethysmography in patients with fibromyalgia syndrome (Castro-Sánchez, dkk, 2020) ¹⁸	n=74 subjects age=18-68 years old condition=FM S, experienced pain for at least 3 days within the 30-day period prior to the intervention	Group 1=Dry Needling Group 2=TENS	Pain scores: Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) and Short-form McGill Pain Questionnaire (SF-MPQ) Heart rate, galvanic skin response, SpO ₂ , and photoplethysmography: Electro Sensor Complex v.2.5.	- ANOVA showed significant differences between groups for pain dimensions (sensory, affective, total), VAS (P=0.001), and heart rate variability in very low frequency (P=0.008) and low frequency (P=0.033). - No significant differences were found between the dry needling and TENS groups in the spectral analysis of photoplethysmography and SpO ₂ .
Efficacy of dry needling as an adjunct to manual therapy for patients with chronic mechanical neck pain: a randomised clinical trial (Gallego-Sendarrubias, dkk, 2020) ¹⁹	n=101 subjects age=18-55 years old condition=chronic mechanical neck pain	Group 1=Dry Needling and manual therapy Group 2=Sham Dry Needling and manual therapy	Pain Scores: Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) Pressure Pain Threshold: Digital Algesimeter (Wagner Force Dial FDK 20) ROM: Universal Goniometer	- After 4 weeks, there was a reduction in pain of 4.89±0.27 points from baseline on the NPRS. A statistically significant difference was also observed in PPT between the intervention and control groups (P<0.001). - Cervical ROM showed a statistically significant difference. After 4 weeks, there was a statistically significant reduction in NDI between the two groups (P<0.001).
Immediate Effects of Dry Needling and Myofascial Release on Local and Widespread Pressure Pain Threshold in Individuals With	n=44 subjects age=18-50 years old condition=chronic neck pain with myofascial	Group 1= Dry Needling Group 2= Sham Dry Needling Group 3=Myofascial Release Technique	Pressure Pain Threshold: Digital Algometer (FPX 25; Wagner Instruments, Greenwich, Connecticut) Neck Pain: Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS)	- There is a main effect of time on both the treated side (F = 4.917, P = 0.001) and the contralateral side (F = 4.70, P = 0.015), with DN and MR increasing PPT in UTM.

Active Upper Trapezius Trigger Points: A Randomized Clinical Trial (Stieven, dkk, 2021) ²⁰	trigger points (MTrP)			- Group analysis showed a significant increase in PPT on both the ipsilateral and contralateral sides for both DN and MR. Neck pain decreased after DN ($P < 0.001$), MR ($P < 0.001$), and sham DN ($P = 0.008$).
Dry needling in active or latent trigger point in patients with neck pain: a randomized clinical trial (Martín-Sacristán, dkk, 2022) ²¹	n=65 subjects age=18-65 years old condition=non-specific neck pain for the last 3 months	Group 1= Dry needling on active MTrP Group 2= Dry needling on laten MTrP Group 3=Dry needling on non-MTrP	Pain: Neck Disability Index (NDI) Pressure Pain Threshold: Digital Algometer	- Pain intensity decreased similarly at all points treated with deep dry needling in the muscle. - In terms of pain, the group receiving dry needling at active MTrP experienced a reduction, but the group with active MTrP had the greatest decrease in pain after 1 week.
The effectiveness of dry needling in patients with chronic low back pain: a prospective, randomized, single-blinded study (Rajfur, dkk, 2022) ¹⁵	n=40 subjects age=36-76 years old condition= chronic low back pain due to L5-S1 discopathy	Group 1= Dry Needling (DN) based on the Five Regulatory Systems (FRS) concept Group 2= Sham Dry Needling	Pain: Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) Functional: Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) ROM: Schober Test	- For all measurements, a significant difference ($p < 0.001$) was observed favoring DN compared to the control.
Effect of dry needling on lumbar muscle stiffness in patients with low back pain: A double blind, randomized controlled trial using shear wave elastography (Koppenhaver, dkk, 2022) ²²	n=60 subjects age=18-65 years old condition= Low Back Pain (LBP) with minimal physical disability (ODI score of at least 10%)	Group 1= Dry Needling Group 2= Sham Dry Needling	Muscle Stiffness: Shear Wave Elastography (SWE) Pain: Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) Functional: Oswestry Disability Index (ODI)	- Resting muscle tension of the erector spinae was lower in individuals receiving dry needling compared to those receiving sham dry needling 1 week after treatment, after adjusting for initial differences ($p = 0.019$). - Both the dry needling group and the sham dry needling group reported a statistically significant improvement in both pain (NPRS) and disability related to LBP (ODI).
Efficacy of quadriceps vastus medialis dry needling in a	n=44 subjects age=18-55 years old	Group 1=Rehabilitation protocol and Dry Needling	Pain: Visual Analogue Scale (VAS)	- Both intervention groups showed a statistically significant difference

rehabilitation protocol after surgical reconstruction of complete anterior cruciate ligament rupture (Velázquez-Saornil, dkk, 2017) ²³	condition= Subacute patient post-ACL reconstruction	Group 2= Rehabilitation protocol	ROM: Universal Goniometer Stability: Star Excursion Balance Test (SEBT) Functional: Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index (WOMAC)	(P<0.001), with a greater effect for reducing VAS and WOMAC, and increasing ROM and SEBT in the dry needling group.
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DISCUSSION

The results from various studies indicate that dry needling is an effective intervention for reducing pain in several musculoskeletal conditions, such as fibromyalgia syndrome (FMS), chronic mechanical neck pain, and chronic low back pain. In the study conducted by Castro-Sánchez et al, dry needling was shown to produce a significant reduction in pain compared to TENS therapy in patients with FMS.¹⁸ Similarly, in the study by Gallego-Sendarrubias et al, dry needling as part of manual therapy resulted in a meaningful reduction in pain after a 4-week intervention period in patients with chronic mechanical neck pain.¹⁹

In the study conducted by Stieven et al, dry needling significantly reduced neck pain in individuals with active trigger points in the upper trapezius, demonstrating its effectiveness in addressing acute pain at trigger points.²⁰ Consistently, dry needling has also been shown to increase pressure pain tolerance at trigger points, as evidenced by improvements in Pressure Pain Threshold (PPT) in various studies.^{19,21,22}

Additionally, dry needling has a positive impact on range of motion (ROM) and functionality in patients with chronic low back pain and post-anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) reconstruction, as demonstrated in studies by Gallego-Sendarrubias et al and Velázquez-Saornil et al.^{19,23} Therefore, the overall results of

the studies suggest that dry needling is a promising therapy in the management of musculoskeletal pain, with the potential to enhance patients' quality of life through pain reduction and improved bodily functionality.

Although the study results indicate the potential effectiveness of dry needling in reducing musculoskeletal pain, it is important to recognize the need for further research to validate these findings and address the limitations of existing studies. Additionally, variations in dry needling techniques among researchers and individual patient characteristics, such as pain location and severity, must be considered when designing optimal interventions. The generalizability of these results also depends on the clinical setting and patient population studied, making it essential to consider evidence from existing research before determining whether dry needling is an appropriate therapeutic option in a specific clinical context. These findings provide valuable insights for clinical practice by highlighting the effectiveness of dry needling in reducing musculoskeletal pain and improving functional outcomes in conditions such as low back pain and neck pain. They also underscore the importance of considering individual patient characteristics and existing research evidence when selecting the most appropriate therapy in a given clinical context. Thus, these findings can assist healthcare practitioners in making optimal

care decisions and guide patients in choosing therapy options that meet their needs.

Furthermore, these findings may serve as a basis for health policy-making that takes into account the potential benefits and limitations of dry needling therapy in managing musculoskeletal pain. However, it is important to note that the studies presented have several limitations, including the lack of appropriate control groups, variations in dry needling techniques, and small sample sizes. Additionally, assessing risk of bias at the study level and overall review limitations should also be considered. Analysis of potential reporting biases and data collection shortcomings can provide additional perspectives in evaluating the reliability of findings in a clinical context.

The review results indicate that dry needling therapy is effective in reducing musculoskeletal pain, such as low back pain, neck pain, and fibromyalgia. However, further research with more robust designs is needed to validate these findings. Implications for future research include addressing limitations in existing studies and exploring the mechanisms of action and factors influencing patient response. In conclusion, dry needling has potential as an effective therapeutic option, but further research is required to strengthen the evidence and understand its optimal use in clinical practice.

CONCLUSION

This literature review indicates that, overall, dry needling (DN) has potential as an effective therapy for reducing musculoskeletal pain in the short term. Several studies suggest that DN may be more effective than no intervention or placebo in reducing pain intensity, as well as improving physical function and quality of life. However, the quality of outcomes still varies among the evaluated studies, and some research has methodological limitations that need to be addressed.

Therefore, while these findings affirm DN's potential as a beneficial adjunctive therapy, further research with more robust designs and larger population samples is required to validate its effectiveness across various musculoskeletal conditions. Clinical practitioners should carefully consider the existing evidence before adopting DN in their practice, while remaining open to ongoing research to enhance understanding of DN's role in managing musculoskeletal pain.

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